

REASONS FOR CHOOSING MODELS OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH OF PRIMARY SCHOOLCHILDREN

Tursunova Saida Isakovna

Teacher of the department

Primary education Termez State pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10155214>

Abstract. *The content of the article shows the formation of oral speech skills in primary schoolchildren, literate development of speech and thinking, error-free writing, mastering the skills of written and oral communication, nurturing a positive emotional and holistic attitude towards the development of oral speech, awakening cognitive interest in oral speech. The article is intended for specialist managers and deputy heads of general education institutions and institutions of additional education for schoolchildren, as well as teachers implementing extracurricular activities.*

Keywords: *extracurricular part, plan, goals, principles, values, to achieve, important tasks, aimed, humanistic, per week, development of intelligence, effective ways, exercises, didactic and educational games, reliably, fill out an electronic journal, take into account.*

Extracurricular activities are part of the curriculum. The curriculum is a component of the basic educational program of primary general education and basic general education. The curriculum consists of two parts: an invariant part and a variable part, including extracurricular activities.

The extracurricular part is formed by the participants in the educational process independently, providing regional features of the content of education and the individual needs of the student.

The development and description of models for organizing extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren in various conditions of the educational process is carried out on the basis of regulatory documents at the federal level and methodological recommendations of the developers of the federal state educational standard for primary general education. List of normative documents and methodological recommendations ensuring the implementation of extracurricular activities. When an educational institution chooses models for organizing extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren in various conditions of implementation of the educational process, the following positions are considered:

-the main educational program of primary general education is implemented by the educational institution through the curriculum and extracurricular activities;

-the plan for extracurricular activities is one of the main organizational mechanisms for the implementation of the basic educational program of primary general education of an educational institution;

-the plan for extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren ensures that the individual characteristics and needs of students are taken into account through the organization of extracurricular activities;

-the plan for extracurricular activities of an educational institution determines the composition and structure of directions, forms of organization, volume of extracurricular activities for each student or group of students at the level of primary general education (up to 1350 hours for four years of study);

-the educational institution independently develops and approves a plan for extracurricular activities;

-extracurricular activities are organized by the educational institution in the areas of personal development (sports and recreational, spiritual and moral, social, general intellectual, general cultural);

-extracurricular activities are organized through such forms as excursions, clubs, sections, round tables, conferences, debates, school scientific societies, olympiads, competitions, search and scientific research, socially useful practices;

-when describing tasks, choosing organizational and content models, creating conditions, developing programs for the implementation of extracurricular activities for an educational institution.

-extracurricular activities in an educational institution must correspond to the goals, principles, values reflected in the basic educational program of primary general education, the educational system of the school;

-the choice of models, forms of organization of extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren is determined by the educational institution independently based on an analysis of the totality of conditions for the implementation of the educational process.

Extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren can be considered as a process of interaction between teachers and students in the course of educational activities, carried out in forms other than classroom lessons, and aimed at achieving the planned results of mastering the basic educational program of primary general education. In addition, extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of younger schoolchildren in elementary school make it possible to solve a number of very important problems:

- ensure favorable adaptation of the child at school;
- optimize students' workload; □ improve conditions for the development of the child;
- take into account the age and individual characteristics of students. The advantages of using extracurricular activities to consolidate and practically use certain aspects of the content of academic subjects and courses are also obvious.

Extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren are organized with a class or a group of students in order to ensure their individual needs and interests. Extracurricular activities are aimed at the formation of personal, cognitive and communicative universal educational activities and have a pronounced educational and socio-pedagogical orientation.

At primary school age, rapid development of intellect occurs. The opportunity to develop abilities is very high. The development of cognitive abilities of primary schoolchildren in the development of oral language today remains the least developed methodological problem. Many

teachers and psychologists express the opinion that primary school is a “high-risk zone”, since it is at the stage of primary education, due to the predominant orientation of teachers towards mastering knowledge, skills and abilities, that the development of abilities in many children is blocked. It is important not to miss this moment and find effective ways to develop children's abilities. Despite the constant improvement of forms and methods of work, there are significant gaps in the development of cognitive abilities in oral speech. Previously, the student was completely subordinate to the teacher, now active actions, thoughts, ideas and doubts are expected from him. Most classes contain children of different levels of readiness, which requires tasks of different levels of difficulty. The teacher must develop any student according to individual abilities and identify the creative capabilities of each individual. Each lesson lasts 35 minutes. During classes, the student develops developed forms of self-awareness, self-control and self-esteem. The absence of grades reduces anxiety and unreasonable worry among students, and the fear of wrong answers disappears. As a result, children develop an attitude towards these activities as a means of developing their personality. The classes use entertaining and easy-to-understand tasks and exercises, tasks, questions, riddles, games, puzzles, crosswords, which is attractive for younger schoolchildren to develop oral speech. Most of the time in class is occupied by children independently solving search problems. Thanks to this, children develop the ability to act independently, make decisions, speak correctly, and manage themselves in difficult situations. Through new approaches, methods, and technologies, promote the speech development of children. A child's oral speech skills are formed under the influence of many factors. That is why it is so important to create conditions for children's speech activity, for communication, for expressing their thoughts.

The improvement and development of content and organizational forms for the implementation of extracurricular activities will be carried out more effectively if the following principles are observed:

1. The principle of a humanistic orientation, which presupposes the teacher's attitude towards students as responsible subjects of their own development, the subject-subject nature of the relationship, the provision of psychological and pedagogical support in self-knowledge, self-determination and self-realization of the individual.

2. The principle of consistency, which assumes that extracurricular activities and the development of oral speech ensure integrity, continuity and interrelation between: - the main components of the organized activity (target, content, procedural, technological and effective);

- lesson and educational activities;
- all participants in extracurricular activities (teachers, students, parents, social partners, etc.);
- regional, school-wide, classroom, individual systems of education and additional education.
- individual systems of upbringing and additional education.

The duration of classes and their number per week are determined by the teacher's educational program, as well as the requirements for the children's activity schedule at school (35-45-70 minutes). In accordance with the program, the teacher can use various forms of educational activities: classroom and extracurricular activities. The forms of extracurricular activities are different from the lesson. Change between extracurricular activities lasting at least 10 minutes.

Responsibilities of teachers for extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren:

- reliably fill out electronic logs for extracurricular activities;
- register the presence or absence of a student at an extracurricular lesson;
- on the “lesson topics and assignments” page, timely write down the topic of the extracurricular lesson, fill out the electronic journal directly on the day of the extracurricular lesson, if there is no technical possibility - the next day, but no later than two days from the date of the extracurricular lesson on the development of oral speech. The journal is a financial document, so when filling it out, it is necessary to take into account the monthly movement of students.

Conclusion

When organizing extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren in various conditions of the educational process, the principle of illustration and clarity in teaching remains leading in teaching, since the peculiarity of primary schoolchildren is: visual-figurative thinking, reading poems.

Taking this feature into account, we create visual aids, tables, diagrams, drawings, from which the child can draw, expressively read, read information syllable by syllable: read correctly, analyze, summarize, voice, characterize. It should be noted that all manuals are simple and understandable. In addition, emotional and intellectual illustration also involves the use of such techniques as dramatization of literary works, fairy tales, proverbs, which contributes to the development of the spiritual and moral sphere through the development of ethical feelings, goodwill and emotional and moral responsiveness, understanding and empathy for the feelings of other people. And the most important thing is to master the skills of semantic reading of Russian texts of various styles and genres. That is why we consider “Children’s Theater” to be one of the important areas of extracurricular activities for the development of oral speech. We have been teaching this course in schools for several years now. With performances and productions, our students annually perform oral readings in front of elementary school students and parents. We share our best practices with colleagues and help them in their work. She introduced teachers to the peculiarities of her work and at seminars, speaking at round tables, and conducted open lessons in schools in the city of Termez, the Republic of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. 1.Yu. Yu. Baranova, A. V. Kislyakov, Yu. V. Rebikova, L. N. Chipysheva; edited by M. I. Solodkova, A. V. Kislyakova, Yu. Yu. Baranova Modeling extracurricular activities of students in various conditions of organizing the educational process: Methodological recommendations / authors compilers: - Chelyabinsk: Publishing house “Poligraph-master”, 2011. -93 p. UDC 371.8 BBK 74.200.58 M 74 M 74
2. L. I. Ponomareva Tursunova S. I. Theoretical foundations of the problem of teaching elementary schoolchildren the elements of reasoning in the process of getting to know works of art. Bulletin of Shadrinsk State Pedagogical University Scientific journal of ShSPU, 2023, No. 2 art. 53-58
3. Regulations on the organization of extracurricular activities according to the Federal State Educational Standard of the NOO LLC Municipal Educational Institution - Information and Technological Lyceum No. 24 of Neryungri named after E.A. Varshavsky

4. Tursunova Saida Isakovna, «Methods of teaching Russian to junior schoolchildren», Magazine - Society and Innovation, Termez State Pedagogical Institute - Society and innovations Journal home page: <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/inde>
5. Abzairov Takhir Yuldashevich, “Formation of a linguistic personality in a modern university.” Teacher of the department of Russian language and literature Termez State Pedagogical Institute, <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8059585>
6. T.Yu. Abzairov “Features and methods of teaching the Russian language in universities of Uzbekistan”, Termez State Pedagogical Institute, WWW.bestpublikation.uz ISSN: 2181-3302, SJIF (2022): 4.621, 10/19/2022.
7. S.I. Tursunova Development of oral speech of primary schoolchildren in extracurricular activities, Termez State Pedagogical Institute, Eurasian Research Bulletin, November, 2022-11-30, <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/index>
8. S.I. Tursunova, Development of oral speech of primary school students in national schools as a linguistic and methodological problem, Termez State Pedagogical Institute, Eurasian journal of academic research, 2022-10-24 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7243541>
9. S.I. Tursunova, Theoretical foundations of the problem of teaching elementary schoolchildren the elements of reasoning in the process of getting acquainted with works of art, Termez State Pedagogical Institute, "Bulletin" Shadrinsk 2023 2(58) Russia, 2023-06-21 http://vestnik.shgpi.edu.ru/journal/issue/view/26/Vestnik_2%2858%29_2023
10. T.Yu. Abzairov “Education and training in schools should be harmonious with the idea of national spirit and patriotism.” Termez State Pedagogical Institute, International Scientific research journal (wos) <https://academiascience.org/>
11. T.Yu. Abzairov “Ways to improve spelling literacy in Russian language lessons in secondary school,” Termez State Pedagogical Institute, Eurasian journal of academic research: 2 pp. 57-63 (5). <https://zenodo.org/record/6529280/files/V2I5-57.pdf?download=1>
12. Allaberganova Y., Tursunova S. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINF O‘QUVCHILARINI MILLIY QADRIYATLAR RUHIDA TARBIYALASH //Interpretation and researches. -2023. - T. 2. -No. 1.
13. Tokhtaevna S. M., Tursunova S. I. PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF USING NATIONAL HERITAGE IN EDUCATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS //American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. - 2023. -T. 11. - P. 66-70.
14. Isakovna T. S. et al. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINF O‘QUVCHILARINI TARBIYALASHDA XALQ OG‘ZAKI IJODINING O‘RNI //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2023. -T. 36. - No. 1. - pp. 67-71
15. Tursunova, S. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QUVCHILARIDA OG'ZAKI NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISH, TILSHUNOSLIK USLUBIY MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Interpretation and Researches, 2(1). retrieved from <http://interpretationandresearches.uz/index.php/iar/article/view/965>
16. Isakovna T. S., Shohsuvarovna N. F. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINF O‘QUVCHILARINI MA‘NAVIY-AXLOQIY TARBIYALASH //PEDAGOGS jurnali. - 2022. - T. 23. - No. - pp. 172-177.